

ISic3423

Building inscription on a re-used louterion basin

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building

Material

marble (white)

Object

louterion

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2016.09.28 (Metcalfe)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Phintias

Place of origin (modern)

Licata

Provenance

Monte Sant'Angelo di Licata, Excavation 2003-2005, sectors 1000 and
2000

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Licata, Museo Archeologico della Badia

Physical Description

Multiple marble fragments (of which three join to make one larger fragment, and a

fourth is approximately contiguous to the main fragment), which appear to form part of the circular basin of a 'louterion'. The remains of a square projection (12 x 12 cm, projecting a further 6 cm from the base) are partly preserved on the reverse of the main fragment, by which the basin was fixed onto the stand.

Dimensions

Height 38 cm

Width 47 cm

Depth 3.25-4.8 cm

Layout

The text is inscribed on the concave inner surface of the basin, over seven lines. The visible vacats suggest that although the text is fragmentary, it only covered seven lines originally. The disposition of the text within the basin implies that the basin, in whole or in part, was re-used for the purposes of the inscription. The text curves slightly, due to the concave surface and form of the basin. The text preserves a clear left margin in lines 3-7. Both letter height and interlineation are uneven.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are broad, square and regular in form. Alpha is very broad; sigma has parallel top and bottom bars; delta, theta and omicron are smaller than the other letters and mid-line; epsilon has a shorter middle bar; pi has a slightly overlapping cross-bar; the mid-point of the mu nearly reaches the lower line; theta is fully closed by the middle bar.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-7: 21-32 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation lines 1 to 7: 1.7-3.2 mm

Text

1. []χήσα ν
2. (vac.unknown) τες (vac.unknown)
3. Νεμήνιος Ἀρχα [γ] ἄθο [υ]
4. Θεόδωρος Ἄκε []
5. τὰν ἐπιμέλει α [ν]
6. ἐποίησαντο τ [ᾶς]
7. δομᾶς τοῦ τ []

Apparatus

Text of Campagna 2013

Translation (en)

Nemenios son of Archagathos and Theodoros son of Ake[---] , as (?), gymnasarchs, took care of the construction of the [---]

Commentary

Fragments of a marble louterion basin found in secondary deposition (layers of soil and material slipping down the hillside), and bearing most of a 7-line building inscription recording work by two individuals, Nemenios and Theodoros, holding an uncertain office (gymnasiarch fits in line 1, but not certain), and carrying out a building work (rare word δομή perhaps of a wall (plausible restoration)). The nature and disposition of the text strongly suggests that this is the reuse of part of the basin to carry the inscription. Full discussion

in Campagna 2013, with reasonable proposal on dating by letter forms, and linking the inscription to a major phase of rebuilding at Phintias in the early period of the Roman provincia.

Digital identifiers:

TM 644818

Bibliography

Campagna, L. 2013. Iscrizioni: un'epigrafe ellenistica sulla curatela di lavori edili. In La Torre, G.F., Mollo, F.(eds.), *Finziade I. Scavi sul Monte Sant'Angelo di Licata (2003-2005)*. Rome. pp. 391-401.

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3423. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358498>

Photo Metcalfe